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Multidisciplinary optimal design for improved personalized bioactive glass/ceramic bone substitute implants

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION:

Clinical challenges often overload healthcare systems, particularly in cases involving the musculoskeletal system, which is highly vulnerable to aging and trauma. To address the significant need for bone-substitute implants, new approaches are essential. These solutions should include personalized treatments for improved patient outcomes, advancements in materials for greater mechanical durability without compromising bioactivity or bioresorbability, and improved manufacturing methods to ensure high-quality and reliable products.

In this presentation the approach pursued within the ReBone Doctoral Network (<https://rebone.eu/>), a four-year program funded by the Europe Horizon Marie Skłodowska-Curie initiative, will be shown. This program aims to optimize technologies for creating customized bone-substitute implants using bioactive ceramics and advanced additive manufacturing techniques, thereby tackling the health and societal challenges posed by trauma and bone diseases.

MATERIALS and METHODS: The program establishes a multidisciplinary network and training framework where ten doctoral candidates will collaboratively create an innovative methodology for designing ceramic-based, personalized bone substitute implants. The network, encompassing partners across Europe, integrates expertise in biomechanics, clinical applications, materials engineering, mechanobiology, additive manufacturing, and mixed-reality surgical planning.

Materials are a central focus, emphasizing mechanical properties, bioactivity, biocompatibility, and printing precision. Experts, including biologists, materials engineers, bioengineers, and technology developers, will work together to develop and thoroughly test glass-ceramic-based materials for these implants. Real-case scenarios will be derived from four selected clinical cases requiring bone repair, enabling the creation of personalized, multi-scale implant models. These models will integrate clinical data, optimizing the implant's architecture, material properties, and manufacturing parameters to deliver improved mechanical performance tailored to the anatomical location and shape of the implant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: In the proposed presentation, a general overview of the approach pursued in the project and preliminary results achieved will be shown, with particular reference, but not limited to, the design strategies and material selections adopted in the project.

CONCLUSIONS: The ReBone Doctoral Network, supported by the Europe Horizon Marie Skłodowska-Curie initiative, seeks to resolve challenges related to bone-substitute implants for critical-sized bone defects. This multidisciplinary effort prioritizes technological and material innovations as the basis for designing personalized solutions that address these pressing clinical needs.